

ADVANCED REVIEW OPEN ACCESS

Critical Review for One-Class Classification: Recent Advances and Reality Behind Them

Toshitaka Hayashi¹

¹Faculty of Science, University of Hradec Kralove, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic | ²Malaysia-Japan International Institute of Technology, University Teknologi Malaysia, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia | ³Regional Research Center, Iwate Prefectural University, Takizawa, Japan

Correspondence: Hamido Fujita ([hfujita-799@acm.org](mailto:hfujiita-799@acm.org))

Received: 20 September 2024 | **Revised:** 3 December 2025 | **Accepted:** 6 December 2025

Editor-in-Chief: Witold Pedrycz | **Associate Editor:** Mehmed Kantardzic

Keywords: anomaly detection | machine learning | one-class classification | self-supervised learning

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a critical review of one-class classification (OCC). Old articles defined OCC in a vague way, which allowed OCC models to learn from multiple classes. This paper reconsiders the OCC definition, as training data includes solely one class, and samples belonging to other classes are not available. Moreover, the review introduces a new OCC taxonomy consisting of boundary, distance, probability, fake, and subtask-based approaches. Additionally, the article reveals that many OCC algorithms have learned multiple classes. Common violations include accessing unlabeled datasets, importing other datasets, and hyperparameter tuning based on the testing results. In addition, this paper suggests two gray zones in OCC: creating fake datasets and fake OCC problems from scratch, and decomposing samples into smaller units for accessing multiple classes. These gray zones could contribute to future theory to learn from a single class. On the other hand, the application of OCC can use multiple classes; generally, multiple classes outperform a single class. However, the applications will no longer be OCC after learning multiple classes.

This article is categorized under:

Technologies > Machine Learning

Fundamental Concepts of Data and Knowledge > Key Design Issues in Data Mining

Fundamental Concepts of Data and Knowledge > Data Concepts

1 | Introduction

One-class classification (OCC) was defined as a classification problem where the training data is one class. This definition explained three different problems comprehensively:

1. Supervised classification, where training data includes solely one class.
2. Unsupervised outlier detection, where given data are unlabeled normal and abnormal samples.

3. Positive Unlabeled (PU) learning, where training data includes positive and unlabeled samples.

However, this old definition allows OCC to learn multiple classes. Many researchers have proposed OCC algorithms that learn multiple classes and have outperformed the methods that learn solely one class.

This paper reconsiders the definition of OCC as a supervised classification problem, where training data includes solely one class. New definition treats unsupervised outlier detection and

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PU learning as applications of OCC. Moreover, the review establishes a new taxonomy of OCC, comprising boundary, distance, probability, fake, and subtask-based approaches.

2 | Background

Machine learning (ML) has been applied in various applications (Ahmad et al. 2023). Most applications utilize supervised learning, which trains the model with well-labeled training data. However, supervised classification has several issues, such as class imbalance and noise. A significant concern arises from the inability of models to classify data into unknown classes that were not present in the training data. Gathering labels for all possible classes is infeasible for various reasons, including the rarity of some data, the inherent risks associated with collecting certain types of data, or the fact that some classes do not yet exist.

OCC can address the above challenges by classifying data into the target class or other classes. OCC is essential because learning from one class is the most straightforward problem for detecting unseen classes not included in the training stage. Several OCC algorithms have been proposed in the literature; these approaches use the hypothesis to create an arbitrary score function from one class.

2.1 | History of OCC

Minter (1975) proposed the first concept of OCC using the keyword “single-class classification.” The topic was the Bayesian network, where negative samples were missing. However, this keyword did not become popular.

According to a Scopus keyword search, Hush (1989) published the first conference paper containing the keyword “One-class classifier” in 1989. The content focused on training neural networks with one class. Koch et al. (1995) published the first journal paper that applied OCC for synthetic aperture radar automatic target recognition. Subsequently, Moya and Hush (1996) published the first journal paper on the OCC algorithm, using a neural network classifier. However, neural networks were not competitive in the 1990s due to hardware limitations in handling large computational complexity.

Around the 2000s, support vector data description (SVDD) (Tax and Duin 1999, 2004) and one-class support vector machine (OCSVM) (Schölkopf et al. 2001) were proposed; these methods are based on support vector machines (SVM). Moreover, early OCC algorithms, such as local outlier factor (Breunig et al. 2000), isolation forests (Liu et al. 2008), and reconstruction-based methods (Hawkins et al. 2002), were developed around the same time. Meanwhile, neural networks were still underrated due to their high computational complexity.

In the early 2010s, deep learning (DL) gained significant attention and outperformed SVM in supervised image classification. In 2018, Ruff et al. (2018) proposed deep OCC for image data. Subsequently, fake unseen (Oza and Patel 2018) and subtask-based approaches (Golan and El-Yaniv 2018) have been developed.

2.2 | Related Keywords

OCC is related to several keywords, including anomaly detection (AD) (Corwin et al. 1970), novelty detection (Earing 1976), outlier detection (Guttman 1973), out-of-distribution detection (Vyas et al. 2018), and intrusion detection (Earing 1976). AD aims to detect abnormal data and is frequently used as the representative term for all related keywords. Outlier detection is generally synonymous with AD, as an outlier is a synonym for an anomaly.

Novelty detection aims to recognize data that does not yet exist. This task can encompass OCC, where all training data possess an “old” label. Out-of-distribution detection, meanwhile, targets the identification of samples that are not in the training data distribution. These scenarios might include multiple classes in the training data.

Note that these keywords aim to detect specific data, while the goal of OCC is to learn from one class. Table 1 shows the number of articles indexed with these keywords, the oldest papers, and the years they were published. (The number of papers is based on 1st December 2025).

2.3 | Relevant Reviews

Several review papers have been published with the keyword OCC (Khan and Madden 2013; Pimentel et al. 2014; Oliveri 2017; Trittenbach et al. 2021; Ruff et al. 2021; Seliya et al. 2021; Pang et al. 2021; Mašková et al. 2024; Schneider et al. 2025).

Khan and Madden (2013) published the first OCC survey, which categorized OCC algorithms into OCSVM or non-OCSVMs. Subsequently, Pimentel et al. (2014) separated the algorithms into probability-based, density-based, reconstruction-based,

TABLE 1 | Related keywords, number of articles, and the oldest papers.

Searched keyword	Number	The oldest paper
One-class classification	2428	Hush et al. (1992)
One-class classifier	1004	Hush (1989)
One-class learning	2026	Koch and Moya (1994)
Single-class classification	40	Minter (1975)
Anomaly detection	54,312	Corwin et al. (1970)
Novelty detection	2049	Earing (1976)
Outlier detection	11,299	Guttman (1973)
Out-of-distribution detection	820	Vyas et al. (2018)
Intrusion detection	45,116	Earing (1976)

TABLE 2 | The definition of OCC by other articles.

Reviews	Definition of OCC	Number of class
Khan and Madden (2013)	OCC algorithms aim to build classification models when the negative class is either absent, poorly sampled or not well defined.	Not specified
Pimentel et al. (2014)	OCC is usually assumed that the positive class is very well sampled, while the other class(es) is/are severely under-sampled.	Not specified
Oliveri (2017)	OCC verifies whether a sample is compatible or not with the characteristics of a single class of interest (or to one single class at a time, in the case of more than one relevant class). Food science paper.	1
Trittenbach et al. (2021)	The objective of OCC for outlier detection is to learn a decision function that discerns between normal and unusual observations.	Not specified
Ruff et al. (2021)	We can see one-class classification as a particularly tricky classification problem, namely as binary classification where we only have (or almost only have) access to data from one class—the normal class	Not specified
Seliya et al. (2021)	One-class classification is a specific type of multi- or binary-classification where the classification problem is addressed by examining and analyzing instances of only one class, which is usually the class of interest. In an OCC problem scenario, labeled instances of the positive class(es) are either not available or are not in adequate numbers to train a traditional machine learner.	Not specified
Pang et al. (2021)	Not defined. The review was mainly for anomaly detection.	Not specified
Emmert-Streib and Dehmer (2022)	OCC is either based on data containing only positive instances or on data that are a combination of positive and unlabeled instances.	Not specified
Mašková et al. (2024)	Not defined	Not specified
Schneider et al. (2025)	OCC is a class modeling scenario where there is only one target class of interest, and well-represented in the training data. The availability of training data include, learning with target samples only, and with target samples and some non-target ones.	Rigor: 1 Compliant: not specified
This review	OCC is classification problem to learn from solely one class. OCC should not access multiple classes.	1

domain-based, and information-theoretic approaches. However, these taxonomies are outdated and do not align with the current situation, as deep learning was not yet popular.

Besides, Oliveri (2017) discussed OCC in the context of food analysis. Trittenbach et al. (2021) summarized the review of active learning using one-class classifiers, which is related to semi-supervised learning. Emmert-Streib and Dehmer (2022) described OCC in the context of the taxonomy of machine learning paradigms, including PU learning as a subcategory of OCC.

Recently, Ruff et al. (2021), Seliya et al. (2021), and Pang et al. (2021) provided reviews of OCC. The contents included DL and several new materials, such as self-supervised

classification subtasks, outlier exposure, and pre-trained models. Moreover, Mašková et al. (2024) published a review for set AD, where a single “set data” consists of multiple feature vectors. Schneider et al. (2025) provided the AI-assisted review for OCC. They categorized OCC algorithms into rigorous and compliant approaches. This direction was similar to this review; however, they did not explain why the algorithm is compliant as OCC. Table 2 summarizes how other review articles defined OCC.

Most of the review articles did not specify the number of classes in the training data. Schneider et al. (2025) categorized OCC into rigorous and compliant methods. However, their review was made by AI and did not explain why the paper is compliant.

Apart from the previous reviews, this review defines OCC as a supervised classification problem where training data contains solely one class. The new definition treats algorithms covered by the old OCC definition as “application of OCC.”

The contribution and originality are summarized as follows:

- This manuscript concerns the state-of-the-art “OCC algorithms” that learn multiple classes. Such a circumstance is due to the old OCC definition.
- Apart from the previous reviews, this review defines OCC as a supervised classification problem where training data contains solely one class. The new definition treats algorithms covered by the old OCC definition as “application of OCC.”
- The uniqueness of this review is to discuss gray zones between OCC and binary/multi-class classification. The potential gray zones include (1) creating fake datasets and fake OCC problems from scratch, and (2) decomposing one-class samples into smaller units to access multiple classes.

The organization of this paper is as follows: Section 3 reconsiders the OCC definition and taxonomy. Section 4 summarizes OCC algorithms in five categories, while Section 5 reports the application of OCC. Moreover, Section 6 discusses several aspects, including the best OCC algorithms, violations of accessing multiple classes, and the gray zone of OCC. Finally, Section 7 gives the conclusion.

3 | Definition and Taxonomy

This section reconsiders the definition and taxonomy of OCC. Subsection 3.1 describes the definition of OCC, while Subsection 3.2 provides the taxonomy.

3.1 | Definition

This review defines OCC as follows:

1. **OCC** is a supervised classification problem where the training data includes solely one class.
2. **OCC algorithm** is a supervised classification algorithm, which “can” learn from solely one class.
3. **The application of OCC** refers to a system that applies an OCC algorithm. The application can access multiple classes. However, the system will no longer be OCC after accessing more than one class.

The general OCC algorithms aim to classify the data into one class or other classes:

$$\text{OCC}(X) = \begin{cases} \text{One} & (\text{score}(X) \geq \lambda) \\ \text{Other} & (\text{score}(X) < \lambda), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where λ is the threshold value, the score is a likelihood, known as the normal/seen score, which includes the negation of

dissimilarity, referred to as the abnormal/outlier/unseen score. The main challenge in developing the OCC algorithms is to create the score functions.

3.2 | Taxonomy

This survey categorizes OCC algorithms into five groups: boundary, distance, probability, fake, and subtask-based approaches.

The boundary-based approach (Schölkopf et al. 2001; Tax and Duin 2004; Liu et al. 2008) aims to find the boundary between one class and other classes. This approach includes SVM and decision tree-based algorithms. The score corresponds to whether the data is within the boundary.

The distance-based approach (Breunig et al. 2000; Tax and Duin 1998) calculates the distance/similarity to the normal behavior. This approach includes methods that use the nearest neighbors.

The probability-based approach (Minter 1975; Figueiredo and Jain 2002) computes the probability that the target sample belongs to a one class. Bayesian networks and Gaussian Mixture Models fall under this approach.

The fake-based approach (Oza and Patel 2018) creates pseudo-negative samples to modify OCC to binary classification problems between real positive and fake negative samples. The main challenge is how to generate fake samples. The existing techniques include editing training data, applying generative models to training data, or using part of the training data as fake outliers.

The subtask-based approach (Hawkins et al. 2002; Golan and El-Yaniv 2018) calculates scores based on the error or accuracy of subtasks. The idea is to train an arbitrary machine learning model to solve a subtask created from samples belonging to one class. The hypothesis is that the model errors for one class are smaller than those for other classes since the model learns the subtask from solely one class. Previous reviews (Pimentel et al. 2014; Ruff et al. 2021) have referred to this category as a reconstruction-based approach. However, recent studies proposed more subtasks, such as self-labeled classification, knowledge distillation, and transformation. Accordingly, this review updates the category name to a subtask-based approach.

Boundary, distance, and probability-based algorithms are applicable only to feature vectors, while the fake and subtask-based algorithms are applicable to all data types. Moreover, other data types can apply feature extraction methods for executing boundary, distance, and probability-based OCC algorithms. Table 3 summarizes the taxonomy of OCC with brief descriptions for five categories and feature extraction.

4 | One-Class Classification Approaches

Subsections 4.1–4.5 summarize five groups of OCC algorithms described in the previous section, respectively.

TABLE 3 | OCC taxonomy.

Category	Data type	Description
Boundary	Feature	Find a boundary surrounding the one class.
Distance		Compute the distance/similarity from normal data.
Probability		Compute the likelihood of belonging to one class.
Fake	All	Create fake data belonging to other classes.
Subtask		Use the error of subtask.
Feature extraction	Except for feature	Extract feature vectors, and apply feature OCC.

Moreover, Subsection 4.6 describes the feature extraction process for OCC.

4.1 | Boundary-based Approach

The boundary-based approach computes the class boundary in the feature vector space. The existing boundary-based algorithms are categorized into SVM-based or decision tree-based methods.

4.1.1 | One-Class Support Vector Machine

Tax and Duin (1999), Tax and Duin (2004) proposed support vector data description (SVDD), which computes a hypersphere surrounding the data distribution. One class is within the hypersphere, while the outside is the unseen class. A one-class support vector machine (OCSVM) (Schölkopf et al. 2001) considers the mapping function into feature vector space to calculate the linear split. Then, the algorithm computes a hyperplane between mapped samples and the pseudo-outlier, origin O. SVDD and OCSVM are equivalent when the Gaussian kernel is used (Tax and Duin 2004).

Score function of OCSVM is written as follows (Schölkopf et al. 2001):

$$\text{score}_{\text{ocsvm}}(x) = \sum_i^N \alpha_i K(x_i, x), \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of training data, α_i is a weight of x_i ($0 \leq \alpha_i \leq 1/vN$, where v is hyperparameters to control trade-off), and K is a kernel function. Several researchers (Tax and Duin 2004; Lenz et al. 2021) reported that the Gaussian kernel,

also known as RBF (Radial Basis Function), is the best alternative. The RBF kernel is written as:

$$K_{\text{RBF}}(x_i, x) = \exp\left(-\gamma * \|x_i - x\|^2\right) \quad (3)$$

where γ is a hyperparameter, while $\|x_i - x\|^2$ is a L2 distance between the support vector and the input. The Equation (3) can be interpreted as the similarity metric: the maximum value is $\exp(0) = 1$ when x_i and x are identical. In summary, OCSVM computes the score by a weighted sum of similarities between support vectors and the target data.

Subsequently, several variants have been proposed for OCSVM (Alam et al. 2020). Li et al. (2003) pointed out that learning from noises degrades OCSVM results; they removed the noises (i.e., most abnormal training samples) from the training data and improved the classification accuracy.

Hao (2008) applied a fuzzy function to OCSVM. The idea was to assign different weights to training data points, where the model should classify meaningful samples correctly while ignoring meaningless samples. Fuzzy OCSVM assigns data samples to the membership function according to their importance in the class.

Sohrab et al. (2018) proposed subspace support vector data description (S-SVDD) that considers SVDD in optimized low-dimensional subspaces instead of computing all dimensions. Moreover, the same authors proposed Ellipsoidal S-SVDD (ES-SVDD) (Sohrab et al. 2020); the idea was to modify the shape of the boundary from a hypersphere to an ellipsoidal.

4.1.2 | Isolation Forest

Isolation Forest (IF) (Liu et al. 2008) constructs an ensemble of random binary trees to detect outliers. Each tree has internal nodes to partition data, using randomly selected dimensions and threshold values. IF will create internal nodes until one of the following conditions is met:

1. The tree reaches the maximum height.
2. The assigned training subset is only one sample.
3. The assigned training subset has only identical samples.

The hypothesis is that random trees isolate abnormal samples earlier than normal samples. Therefore, the score can be computed by assigning data to the trees, where the abnormal score corresponds to the path length from the root node to the leaf containing the target point.

Liu et al. (2008) proposed the anomaly score by the following equation:

$$\text{score}(X) = 2^{-\frac{E(h(X))}{c(n)}}, \quad (4)$$

where $E(h(X))$ is the average path length that random trees isolate data X .

$$E(h(X)) = \frac{1}{|\text{tree}|} \sum_t^{\text{tree}} h_t(X). \quad (5)$$

In addition, $C(n)$ is a normalization variable to handle the length of the trees. More concretely, $C(n)$ is the expected path lengths required to isolate a sample from n instances:

$$c(n) = 2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \frac{1}{i} \right) - \frac{2(n-1)}{n}. \quad (6)$$

IF has variants regarding the data split process. The initial IF (Liu et al. 2008) considered splits with a single random attribute and a value. Hariri et al. (2019) proposed the Extended Isolation Forest, which creates linear splits involving more than two dimensions. Subsequently, Xu et al. (2023) proposed Deep Isolation Forest by mapping data with an optimization-free neural network. This method can provide a non-linear split since the mapping function is non-linear. Similarly, Ryu et al. (2024) applied untrained neural networks to detect anomalies. The idea was to replace a random tree with a random neural network. IF has an advantage in its processing speed because random functions do not require optimization.

4.2 | Distance-based Approach

A distance-based approach utilizes the distance or similarity. This category includes two subcategories: (1) computing the distance from the normal points or (2) considering the similarity with neighbor training samples.

4.2.1 | Computing the Distance From Normal Points

The main challenge in the first sub-category is deciding the normal point. The most straightforward approach is to use the average of the training data. Another approach is to compute the distance from the nearest training data. Nearest neighbor distance (NND) is the distance between the target and its nearest neighbor (Lenz et al. 2021), while K-distance (KD) is the distance between the target and its K -th nearest neighbor (Breunig et al. 2000).

$$\text{NND}(X) = \|X - \text{NN}^{\text{tr}}(X)\| \quad (7)$$

$$\text{KD}(X) = \|X - K\text{th NN}^{\text{tr}}(X)\| \quad (8)$$

In addition, Choi (2009) proposed the least squares OCSVM, which aimed to extend the least squares SVM (Suykens and Vandewalle 1999) into OCSVM. The method computes a hyperplane that is close to most training samples (regression). While traditional OCSVM is a boundary-based approach, the least squares OCSVM falls into a distance-based approach, where the hyperplane corresponds to the normal class.

4.2.2 | Computing Similarity With Neighbor Samples

Other algorithms compute the similarity with the nearest training samples; if the target data is dissimilar to its neighbors, the sample is classified as an outlier. In the distance-based approach,

a larger distance is more likely to be an outlier. Therefore, several researchers divided the distance from the target samples by the distances from the nearest neighbors. For instance, localized nearest neighbor distance (LNND) is computed by NND for the target sample divided by NND for its neighbor (Tax and Duin 1998; Lenz et al. 2021).

$$\text{LNND}(X) = \frac{\text{NND}(X)}{\text{NND}(\text{NN}^{\text{tr}}(X))} = \frac{\|X - \text{NN}^{\text{tr}}(X)\|}{\|\text{NN}^{\text{tr}}(X) - \text{NN}^{\text{tr}}(\text{NN}^{\text{tr}}(X))\|} \quad (9)$$

Several methods consider density, which is the inverse of distance or the number of neighbors. Apart from distance, a sample with higher density is more likely to belong to one class. Breunig et al. (2000) proposed the Local Outlier Factor (LOF), which compares local reachable density (LRD) between the target and neighbor samples. The computation of LRD requires reachability distance (RD), which is the maximum value between the K-distance for the target sample and those for the K th neighbors (Breunig et al. 2000).

$$\text{RD}(X, A) = \max \{ \text{dist}(X, A), \text{KD}(A) \} \quad (10)$$

LRD is the inverse of the average RD between X and its K neighbors, $\text{KN}(X)$:

$$\text{LRD}_k(X) = \frac{1}{\sum_{X_j \in \text{KN}(X)} \frac{\text{RD}(X, X_j)}{|\text{KN}(X)|}} \quad (11)$$

Note that $|\text{KN}(X)|$ might be larger than k if multiple samples are equally distant from the target sample.

Finally, LOF is the average LRDs of neighbors divided by the LRD of the target:

$$\text{LOF}_k(X) = \frac{\sum_{X_j \in \text{KN}(X)} \text{LRD}_k(X_j)}{|\text{KN}(X)| * \text{LRD}_k(X)} \quad (12)$$

Note that calculating the LRD of neighbor samples requires access to neighbors of neighbor of neighbor samples (Lenz et al. 2021). This aspect leads to the large time complexity for neighbor search.

Several variants have been proposed to reduce the time complexity of LOF (Alghushairy et al. 2020). The local correlation integral (LOCI) computes the density as the number of neighbor samples within a radius around the target sample (Papadimitriou et al. 2003). The LOCI requires less computational complexity than LOF. Moreover, cluster-based LOF computes local density using clusters (He et al. 2003) that can reduce the cost of neighbor search for points outside the assigned cluster. In addition, Average Localized Proximity (Lenz et al. 2021) computes the proximity between the weighted averages of K -distances of the target and neighbor samples. This computation requires access to the neighbor of a neighbor.

4.3 | Probability-based Approach

The initial single-class classification paper (Minter 1975) transformed the formula of the Bayesian classifier by representing

prior and posterior probabilities of other classes with those of the target class. The OCC function was written as:

$$\text{OCC}(X) = \begin{cases} \text{Seen} \left(q_1 p(X|1) \geq \frac{1}{2} p(X) \right) \\ \text{Unseen (otherwise),} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where q_1 is the prior probability of one class, and $p(X|1)$ is the class conditional density function. Moreover, $p(X)$ is the density of X .

Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) (Figueiredo and Jain 2002) is known as an unsupervised clustering algorithm computed by the expectation maximization (EM) algorithm. The score of GMM is the likelihood that data belong to Gaussian distributions.

$$\text{score}(X) = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k N(X | \mu_k, \sigma_k), \quad (14)$$

where μ_k, σ_k, π_k are average, covariance, and the weight of k -th Gaussian distribution. In addition, K is number of Gaussian distributions. Training of GMM repeats expectation-maximization step, where the expectation step assign data to cluster (Gaussian Mixture), while maximization step updates the distribution.

Expectation step computes the probability of data belonging to specific cluster:

$$w_{nk} = \frac{\pi_k N(X_n | \mu_k, \sigma_k)}{\text{score}(X_n)} \quad (15)$$

where w_{nk} refers to weight of data X_n belonging to cluster k .

The maximization step updates the distribution parameters, π_k, μ_k, σ_k :

$$\pi_k = \frac{N_k}{N} \quad (16)$$

$$\mu_k = \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_n w_{nk} X_n \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma_k = \frac{1}{N_k} \sum_n w_{nk} (X_n - \mu_k)(X_n - \mu_k)^T \quad (18)$$

where N is number of data, while N_k is a number of the data belonging to cluster k .

4.4 | Fake-based Approach

This approach generates fake unseen samples and applies binary classification between one and fake classes. The key question is how to generate fake data. The strategies can be categorized into (1) editing training samples, (2) applying generative models to training data, and (3) treating the parts of training data as outliers. The following paragraph summarizes the specific papers for each data type.

4.4.1 | Feature Data

Kang (2022) and Aguilar et al. (2021) treated a subset of the training data as fake outliers. Kang (2022) applied clustering to training data and trained one-versus-all binary classifiers for each cluster. Since all training samples are self-labeled as “one” only once, the models classify normal data into “all” in most cases. On the other hand, samples belonging to unseen classes are classified into “one” with a higher probability because clustering and binary classification processes do not involve these samples.

On the other hand, Aguilar et al. (2021) proposed PBCOCC; the idea was to train the decision tree classifier by treating 10% of the training set (selected randomly) as outliers. Since 90% of the training set is labeled as one class, the model will classify most of the samples into one class. The algorithms repeated the training of decision trees 700 times and applied ensemble learning.

4.4.2 | Image Data

Oza and Patel (2018) created fake outliers by adding random Gaussian noise to training images. Subsequently, they applied a convolutional neural network for binary classification between training images and noise images. On the other hand, Yang et al. (2019) applied a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) to training data. The main concern with this approach is that training data do not support creating these fake unseen samples, making it challenging to deal with real-world data.

4.4.3 | Time Series Data

Zhu et al. (2022) applied adversarial samples as fake outliers. Additionally, Hayashi, Cimr, Fujita, and Cimler (2024) proposed interpretable synthetic signals, which create fake signals by editing the amplitude and cycle of training signals. The idea was to explain the samples classified into unknown classes based on the synthetic signal generation process.

4.4.4 | Text Data

Ouzar et al. (2025) developed a prescription error detection system using interpretable synthetic texts, where one class was valid prescription texts. The authors manipulated the texts by changing the amounts or names of medicines and applied binary classification between valid and pseudo-non-valid prescriptions. The prescriptions classified into fake classes were explained based on the text manipulation process, such as incorrect information or overdoses/underdoses.

4.5 | Subtask-based Approach

This approach utilizes the error of the subtask for OCC. For this purpose, an arbitrary machine learning model is trained to solve the subtask created from one class. The hypothesis is that the model error for one class is smaller than its error for others

because the model learned a subtask for only one class. The general score function is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{score}(X) &= -\text{error}(\text{subtask}(X)) \\ &\text{OR accuracy}(\text{subtask}(X)) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

This method was known as the reconstruction-based method, using an autoencoder (AE). However, recent studies proposed other subtasks. Accordingly, this review updated the group name to a subtask-based approach. The researchers proposed several subtasks: reconstruction, transformation, knowledge distillation, classification, and contrastive learning.

4.5.1 | Reconstruction Subtask

The reconstruction subtask (Hawkins et al. 2002) aims to reconstruct input X from compression F :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Reconstruct} &= X \rightarrow \text{decoder}(\text{encoder}(X)), \\ \text{where encoder: } &X \rightarrow F \text{ and decoder: } F \rightarrow X. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The model error is a distance metric between input and reconstructed output:

$$\text{error}(X) = \|X - \text{Reconstruct}(X)\| \quad (21)$$

For this purpose, using AE is a common solution. AE is a neural network consisting of two networks: an encoder and a decoder. The encoder aims to compress the input, while the decoder reconstructs the input. However, the result is not satisfactory because AE has a strong generalization ability. The researchers have applied variants of AE (Perera et al. 2019; Salehi, Arya, et al. 2021) for the subtask. However, the results did not show significant improvements. Peng et al. (2018) considered the reconstruction subtask for graphs.

Other researchers have explored alternative reconstruction subtasks that do not rely on AE. Lee and Kang (2022) applied transformers, aiming to encode input by attention mechanisms and decode it through a convolutional decoder. Cai et al. (2023) extended the transformation-based reconstruction task in pre-trained feature space, operating under the hypothesis that distinguishing normal and abnormal samples is more effective in feature space than in the raw image domain. However, this method utilized feature extraction with a pre-trained model, which might be the main reason for the improvement.

4.5.2 | Transformation Subtask

The transformation subtask aims to transform data X into ideal output I :

$$\text{Transform: } X \rightarrow I, \quad (22)$$

The error is a distance metric between transformation result and ideal output:

$$\text{error}(X) = \|\text{Transform}(X) - I\| \quad (23)$$

Hayashi et al. (2021) proposed an image transformation network that aims to transform all images into one image, called the goal image. This architecture outperformed the AE-based subtask by reducing the generalization ability of the subtask. Interestingly, the results vary, corresponding to the goal images, suggesting a correlation between the difficulty of the subtask and AUC. Note that this method is not pure OCC if goal images are imported from outside training data.

4.5.3 | Knowledge Distillation Subtask

The knowledge distillation subtask (Salehi, Sadjadi, et al. 2021), also known as the student-teacher network (Bergmann et al. 2020), aims to transfer knowledge from a large model (teacher) to a small model (student). The goal of the student network is to provide the same output as the teacher network:

$$\text{Student: } X \rightarrow \text{Teacher}(X) \quad (24)$$

The error is the distance between the model output.

$$\text{error}(X) = \|\text{Student}(X) - \text{Teacher}(X)\| \quad (25)$$

Salehi, Sadjadi, et al. (2021) proposed knowledge distillation subtasks that aim to transfer knowledge from a large model to a small model. Similarly, Bergmann et al. (2020) introduced a student-teacher network for AD, where the teacher network was a pre-trained model that learned multiple classes.

4.5.4 | Classification Subtask

The classification subtask creates a self-labeled dataset and applies multi-class classification between self-labels. Let the self-labels SL as:

$$\text{SL} = \{0, 1, \dots, k, \dots, Z\}, \text{ where } Z > 0 \text{ and } 0 \leq k \leq Z. \quad (26)$$

The self-labeled data is the transformation of the original data. An arbitrary transformation function T_k generates self-labeled data SELF_k belonging to self-label k :

$$T_k: X \rightarrow \text{SELF}_k. \quad (27)$$

Note that self-label 0 corresponds to the original data. Self-labeled classification (SLC) aims to classify SELF_k into k :

$$\text{SLC: } \text{SELF}_k \rightarrow k \quad (28)$$

The score of SLC is a log-likelihood corresponding to the correct classification results:

$$\text{Score}_{\text{SLC}}(X) = \sum_{k=0}^Z L(\text{SLC}(\text{SELF}_k) = k \mid \text{SELF}_k). \quad (29)$$

The main challenge is how to create the self-labeled dataset. Several strategies have been proposed for each data type:

4.5.4.1 | Feature Data. Hayashi and Fujita (2022) proposed a classification subtask, namely feature slide prediction. The idea was to create a self-labeled dataset by sliding the dimensions of feature vectors. However, the result was not competitive due to the overlapping of self-labeled data.

4.5.4.2 | Image Data. Golan and El-Yaniv (2018) created a self-labeled dataset by geometric transformations, while Gidaris et al. (2018) created self-labeled images by image rotations. Moreover, Ju et al. (2022) normalized the viewpoint of images before the transformation.

4.5.4.3 | Time Series Data. Blázquez-García et al. (2021) proposed the classification of signal multiplication, while Huang et al. (2022) introduced the classification of multiresolution. These subtasks are related to the classification of amplitudes and cycles, respectively.

4.5.4.4 | Graph Data. Liu et al. (2021) developed the binary classification subtask to distinguish if the target node belongs to the subgraphs. On the other hand, Xu et al. (2022) proposed a self-labeled classification of four anomalous views.

4.5.4.5 | General Data. Bergman et al. (2019) proposed a classification subtask for affine transformations, computed by $W \times X + b$. This subtask is applicable to all data types represented by numerical values.

4.5.5 | Contrastive Learning Subtask

Contrastive learning (Chen et al. 2020) is a self-supervised learning framework for feature extraction. The goal is to create an agreement between the training data and its transformation. An agreement refers to extracting the same feature vectors. The error of agreement refers to the similarity between extracted feature vectors or the model outputs.

Tack et al. (2020) proposed a contrastive learning subtask, which calculates the similarity between the transformation of the target data and the most similar transformation of training data:

$$\text{Score}_{\text{CON}}(X) = \max_i \text{sim}(T(Xtr_i), T(X)) * \text{norm}, \quad (30)$$

where i is ID of data, sim is similarity, T is transformation, and norm is a normalization variable to handle the scale of transformation (see details in Tack et al. 2020). The score utilizes the most similar transformation among all training data. Contrastive learning computes the similarity between the target and the nearest training samples by comparing all transformations.

$$\text{Score}_{\text{CONS}}(X) = \sum_{k=1}^Z \text{norm} * \max_i \text{sim}(T_k(X), T_k(Xtr_i)) \quad (31)$$

Tack et al. (2020) combined contrastive learning and self-labeled classification subtasks. The final score was computed by the following equation:

$$\text{Score}_{\text{CSI}}(X) = \text{Score}_{\text{CONS}}(X) + w \text{Score}_{\text{SLC}}(X), \quad (32)$$

where w is the weight of SLC: the original paper set the value as 1. Moreover, applied image transformations were cutout, Sobel, noise, blur, perm, rotation, and shift, where the combination of rotation and shift provided the best AUC score. According to their comparison, transformation unrelated to the color information outperformed those that changed color information.

4.6 | Feature Extraction Approaches

Feature extraction is a process that represents an arbitrary data type as feature vectors. Subsequently, the OCC algorithms (described in previous subsections) classify the extracted vectors. The core of this approach is how to extract feature vectors, where the process has to involve only one class.

The following paragraph summarizes specific papers for each data type.

4.6.1 | Image Data

Ruff et al. (2018) proposed deep support vector data description (DSVDD), which combined AE-based feature extraction and SVDD. The paper is a pioneering baseline for the OCC studies. However, AE-specialized feature vectors in reconstruction, which are not competitive for classification. Successful OCC algorithms should specialize the feature vectors for classification.

Chen et al. (2022) trained a self-supervised classification model and applied a subpart of the network for feature extraction. Subsequently, they classified feature vectors by GMM. Self-supervised classification specializes feature vectors for classification, which significantly outperform AE-based features. However, classification between self-labels might have a gap with the actual other classes.

4.6.2 | Time Series Data

Mauceri et al. (2020) combined dissimilarity-based representations with a one-class nearest neighbor classifier. The experiment used 12 dissimilarity metrics for representation. Hayashi, Cimr, Studnička, et al. (2024) created feature vectors based on clustering results of sliding windows in the signal. The advantage is that the model does not require retraining for different signal lengths. Moreover, Yang et al. (2025) combined AE-based feature extraction and GMM.

4.6.3 | Video Data

Wang and Snoussi (2014), Wang et al. (2018) proposed an optical flow orientation feature (capturing movement information for each video frame) and processed the feature vectors using OCSVM. Chriki et al. (2021) compared DL-based pre-trained and handcrafted features, where the pre-trained features outperformed the handcrafted ones.

4.6.4 | Multimodal Data

Multimodal data refers to information collected from multiple sensors. Such data might be the combination of different data types. Sohrab et al. (2021) applied SVDDs in each modality. These SVDDs correspond to a mapping function to the fusion space. Subsequently, another SVDD is trained to compute the boundary in fused space.

4.6.5 | Text Data

Numerous feature extraction algorithms (Liang et al. 2017; Li et al. 2022) have been proposed for words, sentences, paragraphs, or larger bodies of text, such as books, articles, emails, social media, chats, and websites. In particular, Manevitz and Yousef (2001, 2007) extracted features from the text and applied Manevitz and Yousef (2001) and a subtask-based approach using Manevitz and Yousef (2007). Halvani et al. (2016) applied a distance-based approach for authorship verification. Peng et al. (2014) combined PU learning with OCSVM for text analysis.

4.6.6 | Graph Data

Mygdalis et al. (2016) combined graph embedding and OCSVM. Bandyopadhyay et al. (2020) applied two AEs to represent graphs as feature vectors. Subsequently, they computed a score based on distance and a classification subtask for the extracted feature vectors.

5 | Applications

This section summarizes the application of the OCC framework. Subsection 5.1 explains unsupervised outlier detection, while Subsection 5.2 describes PU learning. Subsection 5.3 presents software tailored for implementing OCC algorithms. Subsection 5.4 discusses the concept of the one-class ensemble, which aims to enhance OCC algorithms or decompose multi-class classification problems. Finally, Subsection 5.5 summarizes real-world applications utilizing OCC methodologies.

5.1 | Unsupervised Outlier Detection

Unsupervised outlier detection (Campos et al. 2016) aims to identify outliers in the unlabeled dataset that contain both normal and abnormal data. OCC algorithms can train the model from an unlabeled dataset by treating all data as one class. The hypothesis is that the dataset includes “mainly” one class. Subsequently, the model is applied to compute anomaly scores, where outliers have relatively high anomaly scores (e.g., Top $N\%$).

5.2 | Positive Unlabeled Learning

PU learning (Bekker and Davis 2020) is a special binary classification problem, where the training data includes positive and unlabeled samples. Several studies treated this problem as OCC. However, PU learning accesses multiple classes for training the

model because unlabeled samples might belong to both positive and negative classes. Accordingly, this paper places PU learning as an application of OCC for binary classification.

The brief process of PU learning is as follows: First, OCC algorithms learn positive data and create the OCC model. Subsequently, the model identifies potential negative classes in unlabeled samples. Finally, one can train a binary classification model to distinguish between the positive and the potential negative classes.

5.3 | Anomaly Detection

AD is an application of OCC, where one class is normal. However, anomaly detection can access other classes because its main goal is to detect anomalies, where the number of trained classes is not important. For this reason, some researchers proposed the AD algorithm to access multiple classes.

Outlier exposure (Hendrycks et al. 2018) imports other datasets as fake outliers. This strategy is simple and outperforms OCC algorithms in the benchmark. Liznerski et al. (2022) analyzed the quantity of exposed outlier samples and demonstrated that even a small number of outlier samples suffices to achieve a high AUC score. However, this approach conflicts with OCC as the imported datasets have multiple classes.

Another approach is to apply pre-trained models for feature extraction. The pre-training model is trained on a large-scale dataset, which contains multiple classes. Therefore, feature vectors extracted from pre-trained models contain information for other classes. Reiss et al. (2021, 2022) applied feature extractors derived from a pre-trained classification model on ImageNet, which contains 1000 classes. Mirzaei et al. (2022) applied a diffusion model for the outlier generation process and utilized the feature extraction from a pre-trained model to classify normal and fake unseen classes. However, these strategies are not OCC because the pre-training involved 1000 classes.

5.4 | One-Class Classifier Ensemble

The one-class ensemble technique combines multiple one-class classifiers. The goal is two-fold: enhancing OCC (Tax and Duin 2001; Giacinto et al. 2008; Krawczyk et al. 2014; Krawczyk and Woźniak 2016) and decomposing binary/multi-class classification into an ensemble of OCCs (Krawczyk et al. 2015, 2018).

5.4.1 | Combining OCC Algorithms to Enhance OCC

Tax and Duin (2001) published the first article to combine multiple OCC algorithms for improving OCC performance. Moreover, Giacinto et al. (2008) extracted feature vectors with three perspectives and trained OCC models for each feature. Subsequently, these models are combined to create an intrusion detection model.

Krawczyk et al. proposed several papers for the ensemble of one-class classifiers. The first paper (Krawczyk et al. 2014)

separated the dataset into clusters and applied OCSVMs for each cluster. Subsequently, an ensemble of all OCSVM models created the final OCC model. The second paper (Krawczyk and Woźniak 2014) discussed diversity measures for the ensemble process. They raised five metrics, including disagreement, entropy, Shannon, energy, and sphere intersection. The third paper (Krawczyk and Woźniak 2016) proposed dynamic selection between 10 OCC classifiers, where classifiers were selected by competence, referring to the classification accuracy of samples belonging to one class. This ensemble strategy determined the threshold values of base OCC models in advance.

On the other hand, boosting is an ensemble strategy for integrating classifiers sequentially. Ratsch et al. (2002) constructed a boosting framework for OCSVM, while Xing and Liu (2020) applied adaboost for OCSVMs. The general idea in boosting is to increase the weight of misclassified samples by the previous learner. In the context of OCC, the misclassified samples have low normal scores.

Hayashi et al. (2025) applied voting and stacking to combine hyperparameters of OCC algorithms. The motivation was to decide hyperparameters without accessing other classes.

5.4.2 | Decomposing Binary/Multi-Class Classification

This strategy decomposes a multi-class classification problem into an ensemble of OCC problems. This method is an application of the OCC strategy, accessing multiple classes. Krawczyk et al. (2015, 2018) proposed the strategy to decompose multi-class classification by one-class classifier ensembles (Krawczyk et al. 2015) and its dynamic ensemble process (Krawczyk et al. 2018). Novotny et al. (2025) applied the same strategy for DL-based image classification, using the reconstruction subtask in the base learner.

5.5 | Software

OCC algorithms have been implemented in various open packages in Python, which can facilitate the application of OCC algorithms. The requirement is to prepare feature vectors for ML input.

Scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al. 2011) is a well-known machine learning package that includes early OCC algorithms, such as OCSVM, LOF, IF, and GMM. Moreover, Lenz et al. (2022) developed the fuzzy-rough-learn package, which includes ALP and several OCC algorithms for feature data. PyOD (Zhao et al. 2019) comprises various AD algorithms for feature data, with a few algorithms tailored for image and time-series data. The package also incorporates variants of early algorithms.

The TODS package (Lai et al. 2020) contains time series outlier detection systems. It aims to detect three types of outliers: point, pattern, and system-wise outliers. TODS supports data processing, time-series processing, feature analysis, and detection algorithms.

The PyGOD (Liu et al. 2024) serves as an outlier detection library for graph data, containing 16 algorithms for graph outlier detection. These are feature extraction algorithms, focusing mainly on the backbone.

5.6 | Practical Applications

OCC algorithms have been applied to several practical applications. Abnormal event detection (Wang and Snoussi 2014; Vyas et al. 2018) aims to distinguish between normal and abnormal events by learning only normal video.

Remote sensing is a classification task of land types on Earth. Traditional supervised learning methods required extensive annotation of all labels. Li et al. (2010) applied OCC (Li and Guo 2010) and PU learning algorithms Li et al. (2010) to reduce the cost.

OCC is a preferable solution for wildfire risk estimation (Ismail and Amarasoma 2023) because it does not require collecting wildfire data through burning nature. Moreover, Xu et al. (2025) proposed an interpretable OCC model for fire detection, which utilized the unimodality (peak) of fire pixels for explanation.

OCC is a suitable solution for the identification task that aims to recognize a specific object due to the lack of negative samples and the absence of future counterexamples. Specific applications include VPN identification (Lv et al. 2023) and software authorship identification (Lupea et al. 2022).

Bot detection (Rodríguez-Ruiz et al. 2020) aims to classify the texts into writers, such as persons or bots. However, the bot can copy the human's text or vice versa, complicating the classification task.

Landmine detection presents a critical challenge in safeguarding human life on the battlefield. For this purpose, Tbarki et al. (2018) classified ground penetrating radar, where one class was landmines.

Additionally, OCC has been applied to various problems, including defect prediction (Shehab et al. 2024), damage detection (Bigoni and Hesthaven 2020; Oliveira et al. 2020), and fault detection (Zhao et al. 2013; Theissler 2017). OCC often outperforms supervised learning in these issues as training data cannot encompass all possible problems.

Healthcare applications, such as fMRI analysis for depression detection (Mourão-Miranda et al. 2011) and pneumonia screening (Zhang et al. 2020), apply OCC. These datasets commonly suffer from a class imbalance between normal and diseased patients. OCC offers an advantage by training only healthy patients, thereby mitigating the effects of class imbalance.

In addition, OCC finds applications in food science, including food authentication with food safety (Granato et al. 2018) and crop disease detection (Pantazi et al. 2019), where the data pertains to physical food items, and accessing other classes is challenging. Moreover, collecting anomalous foods may raise ethical concerns.

6 | Discussion

This section discusses issues of OCC. Subsection 6.1 reports a brief comparison of OCC algorithms. Subsection 6.2 concerns binary/multi-class classification algorithms dominating OCC experiments. These two subsections lead to Subsection 6.3, which states that OCC underperforms binary multi-class classification. Subsection 6.4 discusses a gray zone to improve OCC. Finally, Subsection 6.5 suggests future directions.

6.1 | Comparison

This subsection summarizes the experiment results of OCC algorithms. The first subsubsection discusses the general experiment procedure of OCC. Subsequently, the best OCC algorithms for feature vectors, images, and time series datasets are suggested.

6.1.1 | Experiment Procedure

The OCC algorithms are evaluated by modifying benchmark datasets containing multiple classes (Janssens et al. 2009). The experiment selects one target class and treats the remaining classes as other classes. The datasets are separated into either train-test or train-validation-test splits.

A train-test split separates the data into training and test sets. The model is trained on the training set and evaluated on a test set. In contrast, a train-validation-test split creates three sets. The OCC model is trained on a training set, while the validation set is used to assess parameters and hyperparameters of the models. Training and validation steps are repeated to improve the model, and the evaluation of the final model uses the test set.

In the OCC problem, the training and validation sets should contain solely one class. However, validation with a single class is not possible. Therefore, most OCC research uses a training-test split. On the other hand, a train-validation split is utilized for training subtasks. Moreover, one possible strategy is to create pseudo-negative validation samples (Nourmohammadi, Arashloo, and Kittler 2025; Nourmohammadi, Yenicesu, et al. 2025) for validating the model.

6.1.2 | Feature Vector

The researchers have evaluated OCC algorithms with various feature vector datasets. These datasets are categorized into UCI (Asuncion and Newman 2007), KEEL (Derrac et al. 2015), or Imbalance-learn package (Lemařtre et al. 2017).

Janssens et al. (2009) compared five OCC algorithms (LOF, LOCI, K-distance, Parzen windows, and SVDD) on 24 datasets from the UCI repository. Their experiment reports the case in which one class is the majority (the inlier). LOF and SVDD outperformed other methods.

Swersky et al. (2016) compared 11 OCC algorithms using 31 UCI datasets. Their experiments separated the classes into inliers (a single class) and outliers (the remaining classes). Subsequently, the experiments are performed by treating inliers and outliers as one class. OCSVM and LOF show the best AUC when one class is the inlier (single). However, their performances degrade when one class is an outlier (multiple classes).

Lenz et al. (2021) compared nine OCC algorithms using 50 UCI datasets. Their comparison was executed after determining the default (the best) hyperparameter for each algorithm. They determined default hyperparameter values from 246 OCC problems. The ALP and OCSVM statistically outperformed other methods. In addition, the nearest neighbor distance outperformed LOF.

Table 4 shows the comparisons of OCC algorithms reported in Hayashi and Fujita (2022). The dataset is imbalanced learn packages (Lemařtre et al. 2017), which contain 27 datasets. Each dataset contains imbalanced binary classification problems. The result is the average AUC across 27 datasets. Preprocessing used the train-test split at a 6:4 ratio. Subsequently, OCC models are trained on a single class in the training set.

ALP and LOF are the first and second alternatives when one class is the majority. This result suggests that a distance-based approach is a promising solution for learning the majority class. A potential reason is that most samples in big data are unrelated to the testing samples, and only the nearest samples are relevant. On the other hand, OCSVM and GMM achieve the best results when the one class is a minority. These methods capture the distribution of one class. Isolation Forest underperforms other methods in terms of AUC but excels in processing speed. Note

TABLE 4 | Comparison of OCC algorithms in imbalanced learn datasets (Hayashi and Fujita 2022). The best results are marked in bold.

Algorithm	Type	One = minority	One = majority
OCSVM (Schölkopf et al. 2001)	Boundary	76.2	61.4
LOF (Breunig et al. 2000)	Distance	71.9	68.0
IF (Liu et al. 2008)	Boundary	72.0	62.1
GMM (Figueiredo and Jain 2002)	Probability	76.2	66.7
OCAE (Hawkins et al. 2002)	Subtask	64.5	37.4
OCFSP-MLP (Hayashi and Fujita 2022)	Subtask	76.1	56.8
ALP (Lenz et al. 2021)	Distance	(74.4)	72.6

that the ALP result for the minority class is marked in brackets because the algorithm failed for a single dataset due to a lack of training samples (neighbors) to run ALP.

Overall, ALP showed the best result except for the weak point for training small samples. The main reason is the default hyperparameter, the best hyperparameter obtained from 256 OCC problems. The idea of the default hyperparameter is a promising direction for applications. However, 256 OCC problems are made from 256 classes, which violates the fundamental principle of learning from a single class.

Recently, Nourmohammadi, Arashloo, and Kittler (2025); Nourmohammadi, Yenicesu, et al. (2025) claimed that their algorithms outperformed ALP in the UCI dataset. Their methods utilized an ensemble of OCC models and synthetic negative samples for validation. The idea sounds reasonable, yet a reproducing study is required in future work.

6.1.3 | Image Dataset

OCC algorithms have been evaluated with several image datasets, such as MNIST (LeCun et al. 2002), Fashion MNIST (Xiao et al. 2017), CIFAR10, CIFAR100 (Krizhevsky and Hinton 2009), and MVTec (Bergmann et al. 2019). MNIST and Fashion MNIST contain grayscale images for digits and fashion, respectively. CIFAR10 and CIFAR100 are developed from tiny image datasets.

The images are roughly categorized into grayscale or RGB. A grayscale image contains a single channel, while an RGB image contains multiple channels.

The Hyper AI webpage (2025) summarizes state-of-the-art machine learning algorithms. In comparison of the CIFAR10 dataset (Bibliograph), Tack et al. (2020) achieved the best results for pure OCC by combining contrastive learning and self-labeled classification subtasks. On the other hand, several AD algorithms outperformed Tack et al. (2020) by utilizing outlier exposure and pre-trained models. The details are discussed in Subsection 5.2.

6.1.4 | Time Series Dataset

Time-series data remains an underexplored research area for OCC. The main challenge is preprocessing to decide on the signal length. Hayashi, Cimr, Fujita, and Cimler (2024) compared OCC algorithms for time-series data as shown in Table 5. The signals are biometric signals collected from 20 people and were preprocessed into a length of 660. Subsequently, the experiment considered an authentication task: classifying the signal into the holders. In particular, the experiment treats a single person as one class, while the remaining 19 people are in other classes. Subsequently, the signals were randomly split into training and testing sets with an 8:2 ratio. The reported result is an average of five different splits. The comparison was fair because all algorithms used the same testing set. This process was repeated 20 times, and the average AUC scores are reported. The best alternative was Blázquez-García et al. (2021), using the classification subtask of signal multiplication.

Note that this comparison is a limited result for the single dataset. The main challenge is that there is no established benchmark for comparing time series OCC algorithms. Future work should explore fair, neutral datasets. One possible option is to use the UCR time series database (Dau et al. 2019), which contains several benchmark time-series datasets.

6.2 | Concerns With One-Class Experiment for Anomaly Detection

OCC shares connections with several keywords, such as AD, novelty detection, and out-of-distribution detection. While these terms are technically distinct, with OCC focusing on training a model from one class, the others aim to detect specific problems without requiring the model to learn from only one class.

AD is often discussed synonymously with OCC. All OCC algorithms are AD algorithms that exclusively train on normal samples, while not all AD algorithms belong to the OCC category. Typical examples include outlier exposure and pre-trained models.

TABLE 5 | Comparison on authentication task (Hayashi, Cimr, Fujita, and Cimler 2024). The best result is marked in bold.

Alternative	Type	Score function	Average AUC
Hayashi, Cimr, Fujita, and Cimler (2024)	Fake-based	Fake = amplitude change	72.3
		Fake = cycle change	59.5
Mauceri et al. (2020)	Feature extraction + Distance	Kullback Leibler divergence	78.7
		Wasserstein distance	77.4
Hayashi et al. (2022)	Transformation subtask	Transformation error	82.6
Hayashi, Cimr, Studnička, et al. (2024)	Feature extraction + Distance	Distance from cluster balance in training data	82.7
Blázquez-García et al. (2021)	Subtask: Classification of signal multiplication	Accuracy	74.6
		Sum of probability for correct self-labels	88.6

Nevertheless, many researchers evaluated AD algorithms using the OCC setting. Outlier exposure and pre-trained models outperformed OCC algorithms because these methods learned binary and multiple classes, respectively. However, this comparison is unfair, and binary or multi-class classifiers should not be considered SOTA for OCC.

Table 6 compiles a list of SOTA AD algorithms on CIFAR-10. For this purpose, the “Anomaly detection on One-class CIFAR-10” experiment on the Hyper AI (Bibliography) is explored (2025/12/01).

We investigated whether the ranked algorithms involved a pre-trained model or outlier exposure. A notable exception was supervised classification (Kim et al. 2020), evidenced by the statement: “6000 normal and anomaly data images were used

for training MNIST and Fashion-MNIST, and 5000 were used for CIFAR-10.”

Interestingly, the top 11 algorithms learned multiple classes in the OCC experiment. This conceptual misalignment suggests that recent OCC algorithms had to outperform multi-class classifiers to claim SOTA performance. Future researchers can ignore these techniques when comparing OCC algorithms.

Another remark is that reverse distillation (Deng and Li 2022) and IGD (Chen et al. 2022) show low AUC scores despite using the pre-trained models. Perhaps these models lost representation for multi-classes due to overfitting to one class. In support of this hypothesis, several articles mentioned that the fine-tuning of pre-trained models should be limited to a few epochs (Liznerski et al. 2022) or a few layers (Reiss et al. 2021).

TABLE 6 | Ranking of anomaly detection on one-class CIFAR-10.

Rank	Algorithm	AUROC	Learning one class?
1	CLIP (OE) (Liznerski et al. 2022)	99.6	No (pre-trained model, outlier exposure)
2	GeneralAD (Sträter et al. 2024)	99.3	No (pre-trained model)
3	Fake It Till You Make It (Mirzaei et al. 2022)	99.1	No (pre-trained model)
4	BLISS (Goodge et al. 2024)	99.1	No (pre-trained model)
5	PANDA-OE (Reiss et al. 2021)	98.9	No (pre-trained model, outlier exposure)
6	Mean-Shifted Contrastive Loss (Reiss and Hoshen 2023)	98.6	No (pre-trained model)
7	CLIP (zero-shot) (Liznerski et al. 2022)	98.5	No (pre-trained model)
8	DINO-FT (Reiss et al. 2022)	98.4	No (pre-trained model)
9	Transformaly (Cohen and Avidan 2022)	98.3	No (pre-trained model)
10	CAP (Gui et al. 2021)	97.0	No (pre-trained model)
11	PANDA (Reiss et al. 2021)	96.2	No (pre-trained model)
12	CSI (Tack et al. 2020)	94.3	Yes
13	DUIAD (Ye et al. 2021)	92.6	Yes
14	DN2 (Bergman et al. 2020)	92.5	No (pre-trained model)
15	DisAug CLR (Sohn et al. 2020)	92.5	Yes
16	FCDD (Liznerski et al. 2020)	92.0	No (outlier Exposure)
17	IGD (pre-trained SSL) (Chen et al. 2022)	91.25	Yes
18	GAN based AD (Kim et al. 2020)	90.6	No (supervised classification)
19	SSOOD (Hendrycks et al. 2019)	90.1	Yes
20	SSD (Sehwag et al. 2020)	90.0	Yes
21	UTAD (Liu et al. 2021)	88.4	Yes
22	GOAD (Bergman and Hoshen 2019)	88.2	Yes
23	ARNET (Ye et al. 2020)	86.6	Yes
24	Reverse Distillation (Deng and Li 2022)	86.5	No (pre-trained model)
25	ADT (Golan and El-Yaniv 2018)	86.0	Yes
26	IGD (pretrained) (Chen et al. 2022)	83.68	No (pre-trained model)
27	ESAD (Huang et al. 2020)	83.3	No (semi-supervised learning)

To be fair, similar criticisms apply to the authors: Hayashi et al. (2021) proposed a subtask to transform images into an image unrelated to one-class. Moreover, they did hyperparameter tuning after assessing the AUC of the testing data (Hayashi, Cimr, Studnička, et al. 2024). These practices involve multiple classes.

Note that this criticism is meaningless from an application point of view for AD because the goal is to detect anomalies. A pre-trained model learned from multiple classes could be rather beneficial for this purpose. However, OCC is not a tool to highlight the advantages of binary or multi-class classifiers. Instead, different experiments should be considered for a fair evaluation.

6.3 | Binary or Multi-Class Classifiers Outperforms OCC

The circumstances described in Subsections 6.1 and 6.2 suggest that binary/multi-class classifiers outperform OCC. Accessing other classes improves the performance of the OCC algorithm, although the algorithm will no longer be OCC.

Li et al. reported that PU learning (Li et al. 2010) outperforms OCC (Li et al. 2010) because PU learning obtained information from unlabeled data belonging to other classes. Moreover, Leevy et al. (2023) reported that binary/multi-class classifiers surpass OCC because these techniques can compare classes and compute boundaries between them. Nourmohammadi, Arashloo, and Kittler (2025); Nourmohammadi, Yenicesu, et al. (2025) compared the OCC algorithm and a binary classification algorithm, namely “non-pure OCC,” where the non-pure method significantly outperformed pure OCC.

The most successful OCC algorithms use self-supervised classification subtasks. These algorithms create multi-class classification problems from one class. OCC requires an arbitrary trick to create binary or multiple classes without accessing other classes.

6.4 | Gray Zone of OCC

This subsection analyzes the gray zone of OCC. OCC tries to produce a binary classification by learning only one class. Therefore, successful OCC algorithms should be similar to binary/multi-class classification algorithms. In this sense, exploring OCC's gray zone could provide hints for improving OCC.

As a core rule, OCC is a problem to learn only one class, where the algorithms should not involve multiple classes. This rule leads to the following constraints:

- Learning an unlabeled dataset conflicts with OCC because the unlabeled data might belong to other classes. Unsupervised outlier detection and PU learning have a risk of learning multiple classes.
- Using other datasets conflicts with OCC because the data belong to other classes. This rule applies to outlier

exposure and pre-trained models. Outlier exposure imports other datasets as fake outliers, while a pre-trained model learned from a different dataset containing multiple classes.

- Hyperparameter tuning cannot involve evaluation using multiple classes. OCC has to decide hyperparameters without accessing other classes.

On the other hand, OCC has the following gray zones:

- Generating a fake dataset is an acceptable strategy because one can ensure that fake data does not belong to other classes. Kataoka et al. (2020) proposed a pre-training strategy utilizing synthetic images generated from formulas. This strategy is a promising direction for the fake-based OCC. Moreover, a fake dataset can create fake OCC problems, which could lead to insights into OCC problems without access to other classes. One can use fake datasets/OCC problems for hyperparameter tuning.
- Decomposing training samples into smaller units is an acceptable strategy to access multiple classes in OCC problems. The justification is that the annotation focuses on the sample level; smaller units can contain multiple classes. Smaller units could refer to subspace (Sohrab et al. 2018) or sliding windows (Hayashi, Cimr, Studnička, et al. 2024).

Note that this discussion is far from the application perspective. Other researchers do not have to obsess over the OCC concept for application. One straightforward solution is to call all algorithms AD. Nevertheless, binary/multi-class classification algorithms should not use OCC to claim the advantage, which will mislead science.

6.5 | Future Direction

Theoretically, OCC should obsess over the concept of learning from one class. The algorithms should be renamed to anomaly detection if they learn multiple classes. The number of classes should be one in OCC. Although pure OCC is not competitive in the real world, considering the learning process from one class could provide insight into an efficient learning process.

The OCC algorithm requires a trick to increase class labels without accessing other classes. Using fake data will be a key component of future OCC algorithms. Several challenges, such as hyperparameter tuning and threshold decisions, could be addressed with fake datasets and fake OCC problems. One challenge is the gap between fake datasets and the actual testing dataset.

Another idea is to decompose samples until having multiple classes. Generally, the class label corresponds to the entire sample. Therefore, smaller units are not annotated as a single class; these unlabeled units may contain multiple classes. One can decompose OCC into unsupervised outlier detection of small units, which will be modified into PU learning, followed by binary classification. Finally, the result can be integrated for OCC at the sample level.

Subtask-based approach is the most promising direction for pure OCC. Developing other subtasks has further room for exploration. One promising idea is to consider OCC subtasks for OCC (Hayashi, Cimr, and Cimler 2024), which could use all OCC algorithms as subtasks, including state-of-the-art ones. Moreover, one-class ensemble classifiers could be utilized in the subtask.

Another minor direction is extending OCC and AD algorithms to other data types, such as time series or video data. These data types are underexplored compared to feature or image data. Applying image OCC/AD algorithms to other data types is a simple strategy. Moreover, one can explore further combinations of feature extraction and OCC algorithms.

On the other hand, the application of OCCs should use multiple classes. However, it is essential to distinguish between the OCC parts and other parts to handle data leakage. Moreover, researchers should not compare binary/multi-class classification and OCC.

7 | Conclusion

This paper offers a critical review of OCC. The article identifies that the previous OCC definition was vague regarding the number of classes in the training data. This paper suggests re-considering the OCC definition to learn from solely one class. The new taxonomy treats unsupervised outlier detection and PU learning as an application of OCC, which provides a clear boundary between OCC and other related problems. In addition, this review categorizes OCC algorithms into five groups: boundary, distance, probability, fake, and subtask-based approaches.

Additionally, the paper raised concerns about the SOTA OCC algorithms accessing multiple classes. Theoretically, OCC algorithms should not learn multiple classes. Accessing other datasets or unlabeled samples conflicts with OCC because these samples might belong to multiple classes. Furthermore, the paper discussed the theoretical gray zone of OCC; the potential ideas include (1) creating fake datasets and fake OCC problems, and (2) decomposing samples into smaller units for accessing multiple classes. These gray zones could contribute to future OCC without involving other classes. On the other hand, applications of OCC can learn multiple classes. However, the algorithms will no longer be OCC after accessing other classes.

Author Contributions

Toshitaka Hayashi: conceptualization (equal), data curation (equal), validation (equal). **Dalibor Cimr:** data curation (equal), visualization (equal). **Hamido Fujita:** methodology (supporting), supervision (equal), writing – review and editing (supporting). **Richard Cimler:** funding acquisition (equal).

Acknowledgments

This article is supported by an open-access token from the University of Hradec Králové. Open access publishing facilitated by Univerzita Hradec Kralove, as part of the Wiley - CzechELib agreement.

Funding

The publication was supported by the research project “2200/04/2024-2026” as part of the “Competition for 2024-2026 Postdoctoral Job Positions at the University of Hradec Králové,” at the Faculty of Science, University of Hradec Králové. The study is supported by the project “Research of Excellence on Digital Technologies and Wellbeing CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004583,” which is co-financed by Ministry of the Education, Youth and Sports (Czech Republic) and the European Union. This study is supported by JSPS/Japan (Japan Society for the Promotion of Science) KAKENHI (Grants-in-Aid for Scientific Research) #JP23K11235.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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